

TABLES

Table A. SCA Scale-dimensions.

Papers	SCA Scale dimensions	No. Items	SCA scale sources
Abdallah <i>et al.</i> (2021)	SCA	7	Qrunfleh and Tarafdar (2013); Al-Shboul (2017)
Abdelilah <i>et al.</i> (2021)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexibility • Responsiveness • Speed • Competence 	14 (4) (3) (3) (3)	Sharifi and Zhang (1999)
Alam <i>et al.</i> (2019)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alertness • Accessibility • Flexibility • Swiftness • Decisiveness 	24 (3) (2) (6) (5) (6)	Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Alfalla-Luque <i>et al.</i> (2018)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term sensitivity to market • Volume flexibility • Variety flexibility 	8 (2) (3) (3)	Agarwal <i>et al.</i> (2006); Arana-Solares <i>et al.</i> (2011); Charles <i>et al.</i> (2010); Christopher (2000); Khan and Pillania (2008); Lin <i>et al.</i> (2006); Lee (2004); van Hoek <i>et al.</i> (2001); Yusuf <i>et al.</i> (2007) SCA scale validated in Marin-Garcia <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Aljumah (2022)	SCA	8	Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Al-Shboul (2017)	SCA	12	Qrunfleh and Tarafdar (2013); Li (2002)
Altay <i>et al.</i> (2018)	SCA	8	Blome <i>et al.</i> (2013); Gligor and Holcomb (2012a)
Alzoubi and Yanamandra (2020)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alertness • Decisiveness • Flexibility 	N/A	Sharifi and Zhang (2001); van Hoek <i>et al.</i> (2001); Sambamurthy <i>et al.</i> (2003); Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2006); Stank <i>et al.</i> (1996); Li <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Ariadi <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Agile SC strategy	8	Qrunfleh and Tarafdar (2013)
Attia (2015)	SCA	6	Whitten <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Avelar-Sosa <i>et al.</i> (2018)	SCA	5	N/A
Ayoub and Abdallah (2019)	SCA	5	Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2008); Gligor and Holcomb (2014); Dubey <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Baah <i>et al.</i> (2022)	SCA	4	Brusset (2016); Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Blome <i>et al.</i> (2013)	SCA	5	Narasimhan <i>et al.</i> (2006); Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2006) ;
Cadden <i>et al.</i> (2022)	SCA	4	Blome <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Chan <i>et al.</i> (2017)	SCA	8	Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Chen (2019)	SCA	8	Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2002); Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Eckstein <i>et al.</i> (2015)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic sensing • Dynamic flexibility • Dynamic speed 	16 (4) (8) (4)	Overby <i>et al.</i> (2006); Li <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Fernandez-Giordano <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Firm's SCA	12	Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Fosso Wamba and Akter (2019)	SCA	5	Setia and Patel (2013)
Garcia-Alcaraz <i>et al.</i> (2017)	SCA	3	Bevilacqua <i>et al.</i> (2009); Borgianni <i>et al.</i> (2015)

Geyi <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Agile practices (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process alignment • Technology integration • Employee empowerment • Network collaboration • Market sensitivity 	28 (5) (6) (6) (6) (5)	Aslam <i>et al.</i> (2018); Gunasekaran <i>et al.</i> (2018); Carvalho <i>et al.</i> (2017); Martinez-Sanchez and Lahoz-Leo (2018); Lin <i>et al.</i> (2006); Eckstein <i>et al.</i> (2015); Conforto <i>et al.</i> (2014); Bottani (2010); Ketchen and Hult (2007); Lee (2004)
Girdwichai and Somjai (2019)	SCA	5	Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Gligor (2016)	Firm SCA	14	Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Gligor and Holcomb (2012b)	SCA	8	Li <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2020)	SCA	6	Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013, 2016)
Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2022)	SCA	14	Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Firm SCA	14	Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Hu <i>et al.</i> (2022)	SCA	22	Garver and Mentzer (1999)
Hwang and Kim (2018)	SCA	6	Gligor and Holcomb (2014); Li <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Irfan <i>et al.</i> (2019)	SCA	7	Mikalef and Pateli (2017); Rai and Tang (2010); Chan <i>et al.</i> (2017); Li <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Jafari <i>et al.</i> (2021)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alertness • Responsiveness • Decisiveness • Flexibility • Speed 	10 (2) (2) (2) (2) (2)	Zhang and Sharifi (2000); Li <i>et al.</i> (2009); Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Jamjumrus and Sritragool (2019)	SCA	7	Um <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Jermstittiparsert <i>et al.</i> (2019a)	SCA	N/A	N/A
Jermstittiparsert <i>et al.</i> (2019b)	SCA	4	N/A
Kabra and Ramesh (2016)	SCA	6	Hall <i>et al.</i> (2010); Kovacs and Spens (2007); Moon <i>et al.</i> (2012); Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2008); Tatham and Spens (2011); Ye and Wang (2013); Youn <i>et al.</i> (2014)
Khan <i>et al.</i> (2023)	SCA	3	Ayoub and Abdallah (2019)
Khan <i>et al.</i> (2022)	SCA	8	Altay <i>et al.</i> (2018); Whitten <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Liu <i>et al.</i> (2013)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visibility • Joint planning • Process integration • Shared values 	15 (3) (4) (4) (4)	Braunscheidel and Suresh (2009) and Christopher (2005); Simatupang and Sridharan (2005); Lee and Whang (2004); Li and Lin (2006)
Machuca <i>et al.</i> (2021)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term sensitivity to market • Volume flexibility • Variety flexibility 	8 (2) (3) (3)	Marin-Garcia <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Mandal (2016)	SCA	4	Blome <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Mandal (2018)	Health-care agility	5	Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2016); Gligor and Holcomb (2012a); Baltacioglu <i>et al.</i> (2007)
Mandal and Dubey (2020)	Tourism SCA	4	Roy <i>et al.</i> (2016); Mandal <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Manzoor <i>et al.</i> (2022)	SCA	5	N/A
Martinez-Sanchez and Lahoz-Leo (2018)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network based • Virtual • Process integration • Market sensitivity 	21 (5) (3) (5) (8)	Lin <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Mirghafoori <i>et al.</i> (2017)	SCA	14	Bloomfield <i>et al.</i> (1994); Clarke (1959); Mathews (1973); Huang <i>et al.</i> (2005)

Muneer (2019)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market sensitivity • Process integration • Network-based integration • Virtual integration 	21 (8) (5) (5) (3)	Ali and Park (2016)
Najar (2022)	SCA	7	Qi <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Nath and Agrawal (2020)	SCA	6	Mason-Jones and Towill (1999); Goldman <i>et al.</i> (1994); Winter and Knemeyer (2013); Beske (2012). Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Nazempour <i>et al.</i> (2018)	SCA	5	
Panigrahi <i>et al.</i> (2022)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network integration • Virtual integration • Process integration • Customer sensitivity 	15 (6) (4) (3) (2)	Van Hoek <i>et al.</i> (2001); Naylor <i>et al.</i> (1999); Wu (2019).
Prawira <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Agile SC management (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market sensitiveness (MS) • Delivery speed (DS) • Process integration (PI) 	N/A	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2018); Handfield and Pannesi (1992)
Ramos <i>et al.</i> (2023)	SCA	5	Chan <i>et al.</i> (2017); Dubey <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Riquelme-Medina <i>et al.</i> (2022)	SCA	12	Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Samdantsoodol <i>et al.</i> (2017)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsiveness and competency • Flexibility/adaptability • Quickness/speed and quality 	20 (9) (4) (7)	Tseng and Lin (2011); Yusuf <i>et al.</i> (2004)
Sangari and Razmi (2015)	SC agile capabilities (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic alertness • Strategic response capability • Operational alertness • Operational response capability • Episodic alertness • Episodic response capability 	12 (2) (2) (2) (2) (2) (2)	Li <i>et al.</i> (2009)
Tarafdar and Qrunfleh (2016)	Agile SC strategy	5	Huang <i>et al.</i> (2002); Lee (2002); Qi <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Tse <i>et al.</i> (2016)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint Planning • Customer responsiveness • Demand Response 	9 (3) (3) (3)	Braunscheidel and Suresh (2009); Swafford (2003); Christopher (2000); van Hoek <i>et al.</i> (2001)
Um (2017)	SCA	7	N/A
Umam and Sommanawat (2019)	SCA	N/A	Eckstein <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Whitten <i>et al.</i> (2012)	SCA	6	Lee (2004)
Yang (2014)	Firm's SCA	4	Swink <i>et al.</i> (2005)
Zakir <i>et al.</i> (2022)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alertness • Swiftness 	10 (5) (5)	N/A
Zhu and Gao (2021)	SCA	9	Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2016)

Table B. SCA dimensions.

Dimensions	Definition	References
Accessibility	Ability to acquire relevant data quickly (Lu and Ramamurthy, 2011; Tseng and Lin, 2011)	Alam <i>et al.</i> (2019); Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013); Liu <i>et al.</i> (2013); Martinez-Sanchez and Lahoz-Leo (2018); Muneer (2019); Panigrahi <i>et al.</i> (2022)
Alertness	Ability to be alert to threats, sudden changes and opportunities and identify them quickly (Alam <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Li <i>et al.</i> , 2009)	Alzoubi and Yanamandra (2020); Alfalla-Luque <i>et al.</i> (2018); Alam <i>et al.</i> (2019); Jafari <i>et al.</i> (2021); Machuca <i>et al.</i> (2021); Geyi <i>et al.</i> (2020); Martinez-Sanchez and Lahoz-Leo (2018); Muneer (2019); Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013); Li <i>et al.</i> (2009); Zakir <i>et al.</i> (2022); Prawira <i>et al.</i> (2019); Sangari and Razmi (2015); Zakir <i>et al.</i> (2022)
Decisiveness	Supports organisations' decisions with available information (Alam <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Gligor <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	Alam <i>et al.</i> (2019); Alzoubi and Yanamandra (2020); Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013); Jafari <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Flexibility	Ability to update the operations and tactics in implementing the strategy; also understood as the capability for short-term, temporary changes in the supply chain and market environment with the existing supply chain (Samdantsoodol <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Alam <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Eckstein <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	Alam <i>et al.</i> (2019); Alzoubi and Yanamandra (2020); Alfalla-Luque <i>et al.</i> (2018); Abdelilah <i>et al.</i> (2021); Eckstein <i>et al.</i> (2015); Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013); Jafari <i>et al.</i> (2021); Li <i>et al.</i> (2009), Machuca <i>et al.</i> (2021); Samdantsoodol <i>et al.</i> (2017); Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Joint planning	Joint planning or cooperation in operational planning across the supply chain (Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	Geyi <i>et al.</i> (2020); Liu <i>et al.</i> (2013); Martinez-Sanchez and Lahoz-Leo (2018); Muneer (2019); Tse <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Process integration	The term process integration is defined as collaborative operations between suppliers and buyers, common systems, joint product and information-sharing (Prawira <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	Geyi <i>et al.</i> (2020); Liu <i>et al.</i> (2013); Martinez-Sanchez and Lahoz-Leo (2018); Muneer (2019); Panigrahi <i>et al.</i> (2022); Prawira <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Swiftness	Ability of firms to make and rapidly implement decisions on SCM and logistics management (Gligor <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Yusuf <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Lin <i>et al.</i> , 2006)	Alam <i>et al.</i> (2019); Eckstein <i>et al.</i> (2015); Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013); Jafari <i>et al.</i> (2021); Prawira <i>et al.</i> (2019); Samdantsoodol <i>et al.</i> (2017); Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2006); Zakir <i>et al.</i> (2022)

Table C: Characteristics of the main SCA scales.

Scale	SCA construct	Likert scale	Al Humdan <i>et al.</i> (2020)			Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2019)					
			(a)	(b)	(c)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Firm SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alertness • Accessibility • Decisiveness • Swiftness • Flexibility 	1 (strongly disagree) and 7 (strongly agree).	Rapidly	Demand and supply	Reactive and proactive	X	X		X	X	X
Li <i>et al.</i> (2009)	SCA (2 nd -order construct) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic alertness • Strategic response capability • Operational alertness • Operational response capability • Episodic alertness • Episodic response capability 	1 (low) - 5 (high)	Timely manner	Demand and supply	Reactive and proactive		X			X	X
Swafford <i>et al.</i> (2006)	SCA (1 st -order construct)	1 (slow) - 5 (fast)	Fast	Demand and supply	Reactive	X	X		X	X	

(a) Speed; (b) scope of SCA; (c) mode of SCA

(1) ability to quickly change direction; (2) ability to empower the customer; (3) ability to integrate processes within and across firms; (4) ability to speed up operations; (5) ability to adjust tactics and operations (flexibility); (6) ability to scan the environment/anticipate changes

Table D. Journals in the sample.

<i>Sources</i>	<i>Number of articles</i>
Supply Chain Management-an International Journal	5
International Journal of Operations and Production Management	4
International Journal of Production Research	3
International Journal of Supply Chain Management	3
International Journal of Production Economics	2
Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management	2
Operations Management Research	2
Polish Journal of Management Studies	2
Uncertain Supply Chain Management	2
Advances in Production Engineering and Management	1
Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics	1
Baltic Journal of Management	1
Benchmarking-an International Journal	1
Cogent Business and Management	1
Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management	1
Decision Sciences	1
Decision Support Systems	1
Euromed Journal of Business	1
European Journal of Operational Research	1
Expert Systems With Applications	1
Frontiers in Public Health	1
Industrial Management and Data Systems	1
International Journal of Applied Decision Sciences	1
International Journal of Emerging Markets	1
International Journal of Information Systems and Supply Chain Management	1
International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change	1
International Journal of Logistics-Research and Applications	1
International Journal of Logistics Management	1
International Journal of Physical Distribution and Logistics Management	1
International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management	1
International Journal of Services and Operations Management	1
International Journal of Tourism Research	1
Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing	1
Journal of Business Logistics	1
Journal of Business Research	1
Journal of Engineering, Project, and Production Management	1
Journal of Operations Management	1
Management Decision	1
Measuring Business Excellence	1
Pacific Business Review International	1
Production Planning and Control	1
Review of International Business and Strategy	1
Risk Hazards and Crisis in Public Policy	1
Service Business	1
Supply Chain Forum	1
Sustainability	1
TQM Journal	1

Table E. Top 10 SCA-performance articles based on citations.

<i>Authors</i>	<i>Journal</i>	<i>Scopus citations¹</i>	<i>WOS citations²</i>
Liu <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Decision Support Systems	444	364
Blome <i>et al.</i> (2013)	International Journal of Production Research	285	247
Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Journal of Operations Management	278	229
Eckstein <i>et al.</i> (2015)	International Journal of Production Research	242	210
Chan <i>et al.</i> (2017)	European Journal of Operational Research	200	152
Altay <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Production Planning and Control	154	137
Whitten <i>et al.</i> (2012)	International Journal of Operations & Production Management	156	132
Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2012b)	Journal of Business Logistics	143	112
Yang (2014)	International Journal of Production Economics	118	106
Tarafdar and Qrunfleh (2016)	International Journal of Production Research	142	82

¹ Citations received up to October 19, 2022.

² Citations received up to October 26, 2022.

Table F. Principals objectives of the top 10 SCA and performance articles.

<i>Authors</i>	<i>Objectives</i>
Liu <i>et al.</i> (2013)	To propose a model to examine how Information Technology capabilities affect firm performance through absorptive capacity and supply chain agility in the supply chain context.
Blome <i>et al.</i> (2013)	To propose a model that further assesses the influence of supply chain agility on operational performance, as well as its mediating role in the relationship between supply- and demand-side competence and performance.
Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2015)	To examine the association between supply chain agility, cost efficiency and customer effectiveness across various environmental situations.
Eckstein <i>et al.</i> (2015)	To investigate the effects of supply chain agility and supply chain adaptability on cost performance and operational performance.
Chan <i>et al.</i> (2017)	To address the effects of strategic and manufacturing flexibilities and SCA on firm performance in the fashion industry by employing a resource-based perspective as a lens for exploring the major antecedents and consequences of SCA at both the strategic and operational levels.
Altay <i>et al.</i> (2018)	To examine the effects of supply chain agility and supply chain resilience on performance under the moderating effect of organisational culture.
Whitten <i>et al.</i> (2012)	To theorise a Triple-A supply chain performance model that incorporates Triple-A supply chain status as an antecedent to supply chain performance and supply chain performance as an antecedent to organisational performance.
Gligor <i>et al.</i> (2012b)	To examine the relationship between SCA and firm performance, specifically operational and relational results.
Yang (2014)	To develop and empirically test a conceptual framework to investigate the antecedents of manufacturers supply chain agility and the connection of their agility with performance in an emerging economy.
Tarafdar and Qrunfleh (2016)	To examine the mediating effect of supply chain practices on the relationship between agile supply chain strategy and SC performance.

Figure C: Unattenuated funnel plot (Z transformation values).

Combined effect size	Observed	Combined effect size	Adjusted	Heterogeneity	
Fisher z transformations	0.64	Fisher z transformations	0.60	Q	3086.71
SE (z)	0.05	SE (z)	0.06	pQ	0.00
CI Lower limit	0.54	CI Lower limit	0.48	I2	97.93%
CI Upper limit	0.74	CI Upper limit	0.72	T2	0.21
PI Lower limit	-0.14	PI Lower limit	-0.33	T	0.46
PI Upper limit	1.41	PI Upper limit	1.53		

Trim and Fill	On
Estimator for missing studies	Leftmost Run/Rightmost Run
Search from mean	Left
Number of imputed studies	1

Note: the horizontal green line is the PI of the correlations calculated without imputation. CI is the black line in the centre. The horizontal red line shows the scores after trim and fill imputation with the corresponding CI in black.

Figure D: Attenuated funnel plot (Z transformation values).

Combined effect size	Observed	Combined effect size	Adjusted	Heterogeneity	
Fisher z transformations	0.51	Fisher z transformations	0.49	Q	1331.71
SE (z)	0.03	SE (z)	0.03	pQ	0.00
CI Lower limit	0.45	CI Lower limit	0.42	I2	95.12%
CI Upper limit	0.58	CI Upper limit	0.56	T2	0.09
PI Lower limit	0.00	PI Lower limit	-0.10	T	0.30
PI Upper limit	1.03	PI Upper limit	1.08		

Trim and Fill	On
Estimator for missing studies	Leftmost Run/Rightmost Run
Search from mean	Left
Number of imputed studies	2

Note: the horizontal green line is the PI of the correlations calculated without imputation. CI is the black line in the centre. The horizontal red line shows the scores after trim and fill imputation with the corresponding CI in black.

Figure E: Forest plot for attenuated correlations between SC agility and performance.

